

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

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MUNDARIJA

TIJORAT BANKLARIDA MOLIVAVIY HISOBOTLAR TAHLILINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH YO'NALISHLARI	12
Xudoyberdiyev Ulug'bek Axmad o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON KOMPANIYALARIDA DIVIDEND SIYOSATI JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	16
Shermuxamedov Akmal Komiljonovich	
РАЗВИТИЕ МЕХАНИЗМОВ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ МАЛОГО И СРЕДНЕГО БИЗНЕСА В КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКАХ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ФИНТЕХА И ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА	21
Салимова Зиёда Рустамжон қизи	
ELEKTR TARMOQLARI KORXONALARIDA YO'QOTISHLAR HISOBI UCHUN ISHCHI HISOBVARAQLARI TIZIMINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH	27
Xojimurodov Zuxriddin Shukurullo o'g'li	
RAQAMLI MUHITDA BANK XIZMATLARINI MASOFADAN KO'RSATISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	32
Azlarova Aziza Axrorovna	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SOLIQ ORGANLARI FAOLIYATINI SUN'YI INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	36
Soyibova Matluba Ahmedboyevna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATINI STRATEGIK BOSHQARISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	41
M.O. Yo'ldoshova	
NARXLARNI BOSHQARISHNING ZAMONAVIY KONSEPSIYASI SIFATIDA DINAMIK NARX SHAKLLANTIRISH	45
Anvar Deberdiyev	
SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT KO'LAMINI QISQARTIRISH YO'LLARI	49
Mamatkulov Salimjon Raxmonkulovich	
STARTAP EKOTIZIMLARINI RAG'BATLANTIRISHNING SOLIQ MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH: GLOBAL MUAMMOLAR VA HUDUDIY IMKONIYATLAR	55
Ishimova Mohinur Absalomovna	
UMUMIY OVQATLANISH TIZIMIDA B2B MARKETINGINI JORIY ETISH. (XORAZM VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	61
Zakirova Gulnoza Quدراتovna, Aliyeva Gulnora Ildarovna	
TIBBIYOT TASHKIOTLARIDA NOMOLIVAVIY AKTIVLAR HISOBI AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	67
Iskanov Xoljigit Nurkosimovich	
RAQAMLI TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MARKAZIDA ICHKI AUDIT TIZIMINI TASHIL ETISH AMALIYOTI	73
Suyunov Yorqin Bekmurodovich, Nazarov Ubaydulla Abdumannapovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA MONOPOLIYAGA QARSHI SIYOSATNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	79
Yuldashev Akmal Kiyomovich	
TOG'-KON KORXONALARIDA TEXNOLOGIK TIZIM HOLATINI BAHOLASH VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK ZAXIRALARINI ANIQLASH	83
Abirova Nargizabonu	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI VA ULARNING MILLIY RIVOJLANISHI	88
Turayev Abduvohid Kuldashevich	

IQTISODIYOTNING INNOVATSION TARAQQIYOTI SHAROITIDA MEHNAT RESURSLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHDAGI XORIJ MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	93
Artiqova O'g'iljon Zafar qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY TELERADIOKOMPANIYASI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA SEMIR MODELIDAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI	101
Rustamov Zafar	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATI KORXONALARIDA ISHLAB CHIQARISH TANNARXINI PASAYTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARI	107
Metyakubov Azamat Djumanazarovich	
BUXORO ARK ANSAMBLI TURISTIK SIG'IM IMKONIYATLARINI BAHOLASH	111
Sulaymonova Malika Maxmudovna, Qilichov Muhriddin Husniddin o'g'li	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕХАНИЗМОВ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ, КОНТРОЛЯ И АНАЛИЗА ДЕНЕЖНЫХ ПОТОКОВ НА МАЛЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ	116
Муродов Шавкатжон Фарходович, Зайналов Ж. Р.	
XALQARO MOLIYA INSTITUTLARI ISHTIROKIDAGI INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNI AMALGA OSHIRISHDA MAVJUD MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH YO'LLARI	121
Ochildiyeva Naima Mengziya qizi, Ollokulova Feruza Mansurovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING KREDITLASH AMALIYOTIDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	127
Melibayev Sodir Adilovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI RENTABELLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA AKTIVLAR VA REGULYATIV KAPITALNING O'RNI	135
Sheraliev Abbos Xolmuminovich	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF DECISION-MAKING IN THE NATIONAL ELECTRICITY GRID OF UZBEKISTAN	140
Abdumalik A. Djumanov, Mukhlisa M. Gafurova, Tursunmurod R. Sobirov	
VIRTUAL IQTISODIYOTNING SHAKLLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISH MEXANIZMLARI	147
Yuldashev Adhamjon Axadjonovich	
O'ZBEKISTON QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BOZORINING RIVOJLANISH HOLATI VA INSTITUTSIONAL TUZILMASI.....	152
Shamsiddinov Ne'matjon Ashurali o'g'li	
ASOSIY VOSITALAR HISOBI VA AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	157
To'ychiyeva Dilnoza Farxod qizi	
ELEKTRON TIJORAT BOZORIDA RISKLARNI BAHOLASH MASALALARI	162
Aripov Ulug'bek Bahodirovich	
UY-JOY BOZORINI IPOTEKA KREDITLASH AMALIYOTI ORQALI INTEGRATSIYA QILISH: O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI	166
A'zamxo'jayeva Nihola Sulaymon qizi	
HUDUDIY INVESTITSIYA TARKIBINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA DINAMIK TA'SIRINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH (SURXONDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	171
Mirzakulova Risolat Musurmankulovna	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATINI KREDITLASH TARTIBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	175
Bo'taev O'tkir Eshboevich	
KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING INNOVATSION USULLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	181
Umarova Malika Nematjanovna	
РАЗВИТИЕ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ЗЕЛЕННОГО ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ КАК ФАКТОР СТАНОВЛЕНИЯ ЦИРКУЛЯРНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	187
Рахмонов Джамшид Одил угли	

ПРОБЛЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИМИ РЕСУРСАМИ В ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ КУЛЬТУРЫ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	194
Абдусаламова Фарогат Сунатиллаевна	
BANK XIZMATLARI KO'RSATISH MEZONLARINI ANIQLASH VA ULARNI BAHOLASH.....	200
Avazbek Jo'rayev	
BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA EKOLOGIK OMILLARNING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	207
Kuymuratova Matlubaxon Abdimanabovna	
ASALARICHILIK XO'JALIKLARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	211
Berdimuratov Kuanishbay Genjebaevich	
ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ СТЕЙКХОЛДЕРАМИ ПРОЕКТОВ И ПРОГРАММ.....	215
Абдулаттоев Абдухакимжон Абдулхамид угли	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASINING "YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH STRATEGIYASI.....	228
Mohichexra Melikovna Mo'minova	
INKLYUZIV TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH XUSUSIYATLARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA TAHLILI	233
Dilbar Xasanovna Aslanova, Usmanova Zumrad Islamovna	
TA'LIM TIZIMIDA MARKETING YONDASHUVI VA TAMOYILLARINI QO'LLASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	239
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Raxmonova Aziza Tolibovna	
MEHMONXONALAR VA OILAVIY MEHMON UYLARI RIVOJLANISHINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	245
Boynazarov Ulug'bek Egamberdiyevich	
HUDUDLARNING TURISTIK SALOHİYATIDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI ICHKI TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	250
Daminov Mirvoxid Isroilovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT RIVOJLANISHINING BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI: MAKROIQTISODIY VA TARMOQ KO'RSATKICHLARI ASOSIDA TAHLIL	255
Iminoxunov Abdukoxor Abdivaitovich	
OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATI KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONLARINING INNOVATSION SAMARADORLIKKA TA'SIRI	264
Abdunabiyev Sirojiddin G'anijon o'g'li	
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ АКТИВНОСТИ И СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ КАТАЛИЗАТОРОВ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ГИДРООЧИСТКИ НЕФТЕПРОДУКТОВ И ИХ РОЛЬ В ОХРАНЕ ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ.....	271
Тураев Баходир Тиркашевич, Махманов Дониёр Махманович	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATI HUDUDIY TURIZM BOZORINING MARKETING TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDAGI KOMPLEKS TAHLILI	276
Namozov Shahzod Maxmud o'g'li	
INNOVATIVE TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES AND ADVANCED INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN THE FIELD OF AGRICULTURAL SERVICES.....	282
Djurayeva Dilnoza Davronovna, Boltayeva Shakhnoza Bebudovna	
COMPARISON OF HOSPITAL-BASED AND HOME-BASED REHABILITATION AFTER CERVICAL SPINE SURGERY IN UZBEKISTAN	290
Shokhrukh Ziyavaddinov	
O'ZBEKISTON AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARI MOLIYAVIY KOEFFITSIYENTLARI TAHLILI	299
Norqulov Mirsaid To'lqin o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RAQOBAT MUHITINING SHAKLLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI TAHLILI	306
Turdiyev Izatulla Ollaqulovich	
XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA IJARA HISOBI TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	312
Xoliqulova Yulduz Panji qizi	

ELEKTR TARMOQLARI KORXONALARNING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGIGA RAQAMLASHTIRISH VA INNOVATSIYALARNING O'RNI: XORIJ TAJRIBASI	317
Mavlonov Ozod Ulug'bekovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN TARTIBGA SOLISHNING XORIJIY DAVLATLAR ILG'OR TAJRIBALARI VA ULARNI MAMLAKATIMIZDA QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI	322
Rajapov Xayrulla Bekdurdiyevich, Sharipova Lobar Umrbek qizi	
BANK TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH ASOSIDA BOSHQARISHNING ILG'OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALARI.....	330
Boltayev Zokirjon Otanazarovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT TRANSFORMATSIYASI SHAROITIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI TO'LOV QOBILIYATINI TA'MINLASHNING INNOVATSION MEXANIZMLARI.....	334
Adilova Zohida Ikromjonovna	
MOLIYAVIY AKTIVLAR TARKIBIDAGI DEBITORLIK QARZDORLIKLARINI MHXS TALABLARI ASOSIDA BAHOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI	339
Umurzakov Dilshodbek Hakimovich	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА В УСЛОВИЯХ УДАЛЁННОЙ РАБОТЫ	345
Хамидов Далер Дилшодович	
ISMOIL SOMONIY MAQBARASINING TURISTIK SIG'IMINI BAHOLASH: BUXORO TARIXIY MARKAZI MISOLIDA.....	351
Choriyeva Dilovar Tohir qizi, Qilichov Muhridin Husniddin o'g'li	
CONSUMER TRUST IN UZBEKISTAN'S E-COMMERCE	356
Erkin Shavqiyev Professor, Ulugmurodov Farkhod	
IMPROVING THE FINANCING SYSTEM OF EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES.....	362
Karamatdinova Aysawle Parakhatovna	
XORIJIY OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARINING RAQAMLI MARKETING VOSITALARI TAHLILI: O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI	369
Sharopova Nafosat, Xolmamatov Diyorbek	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA MEHNAT BOZORI RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI IJTIMOY-IQTISODIY OMILLARNI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH	374
Islomov Bobur Bahodir o'g'li	
XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA ASOSIY VOSITALARGA AMORTIZATSIYA HISOBLASH USULLARI VA AUDITORLIK HISOBOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	380
Xasanov Shoxrux Raximjonovich	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTINI MODERNIZATSIYALASH SHAROITIDA REAL SEKTOR KORXONALARINING ROLI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	385
Sobitova Ra'no Solidjonovna, Babaxadjayev Firdavs Bahodir o'g'li	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NEW UZBEK CONSULTING SERVICES MARKET AND METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE POTENTIAL FOR ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS	388
Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
RESPUBLIKAMIZDA UMUMIY OVQATLANISH SOHASI XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR VA ULARDAN FOYDALANISH.....	394
Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinova	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA DAVRIDA KORXONA BOSHQARUVINING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	399
Azlarova Munira Muhammad-Amin qizi, Yoqubov Madaminbek Abdurahim o'g'li	
BALIQCILIK SOHASIDA TADBIRKORLIK MAJMUALARINI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN TARTIBGA SOLISHNING ROSSIYA TAJRIBASI VA UNI O'ZBEKISTONDA QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI	406
Rajapov Xayrulla Bekdurdiyevich	

RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLARDA CHIQUINDILARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINING ZAMONAVIY MODELLARI	416
Xasanov Komil Mutalibjanovich	
TOSHKENT VILOYATI QISHLOQ HUDUDLARIDA AYOLLAR TADBIRKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY OMILLARI: EMPIRIK TAHLIL	421
Saidakbarova Ziyoda Doniyor qizi	
METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR FINANCIAL SUPPORT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ADDITIONAL ACTIVITIES IN FARM ENTERPRISES	426
Kalimbetov Khaliknazar Kurbanbaevich	
KIMYO SANOATI KORXONALARIDA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	432
Suyarov Shaxzod Salim o'g'li	
XALQARO MOLIYA TASHKILOTLARIDAN O'ZBEKISTONGA JALB ETILGAN IMTIYOZLI MABLAG'LARNING SAMARADORLIGI	438
Turdiyeva Zarnigor Asqar qizi	
NAVOIY VILOYATIDA TURIZM XIZMATLARINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISH.....	442
Turayev Abduvoxid Kuldashevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT RISKNI BOSHQARISHNING XORIJIY AMALIYOTI.....	448
Turg'unov Nodirbek Muminjanovich	
KORXONALARDA STRATEGIK REJANI ISHLAB CHIQISH DARAJALARI VA BOSQICHLARI	452
Zaripova Sayohat Zafarovna	
IQLIM O'ZGARISHINING AGRAR IQTISODIYOTGA TA'SIRI: NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR VA XALQARO TAJRIBA.....	457
Ozodxon Mahmudovna Qo'ziboyeva, Anvarbekov Fayzullo Rustamjon o'g'li, Rahmonova Xosiyatxon Fayzullo qizi	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF BANKING SERVICES THROUGH THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND BIG DATA TECHNOLOGIES.....	462
Mamatova Sevara Ilhom kizi	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RISK MENEJMENT TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	470
Toshpulatov Davron Akromovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA YASHIL LOYIHALARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH: HOLAT, MUAMMOLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	477
Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNING RASMIY IQTISODIYOTGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH MUAMMOLARI	482
Bobojonov Azimjon Akmal o'g'li	
NAVOIY VILOYATI QIZILQUM CHO'LLARIDA XALQARO TURIZMNI TASHKIL QILISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI.....	486
Turayev Abduvoxid Kuldashevich	
BARQAROR SHAHAR RIVOJLANISHINING ASOSIY OMILLARI VA ULARNING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI: TANLANGAN DAVLATLAR VA O'ZBEKISTON MISOLIDA	493
Dadabayeva Nigora Muxamatxanovna, Jahongirova Muazzamxon Jahongir qizi	
AUDIT TEKSHIRUVLARIDA AUDIT DALILLARINI YIG'ISH AMALIYOTINI ZAMONAVIY IT TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN VA "MACHINE LEARNING" DAN FOYDALANGAN HOLDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ("IPAK YO'LI" AITB MISOLIDA).....	499
Eshqurbonov Bahrom Norsoat o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA OLIY TA'LIM BITIRUVCHILARINING MEHNAT BOZORIGA INTEGRATSIYASI: RAQAMLI KO'NIKMALAR OMILINING ROLI.....	506
Eshbo'riev Umarbek Rashidovich	
KOMPANIYALAR MOLIYASINING BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH YO'LLARI.....	518
Rasulov Jasurbek Abdurasulovich	

ZAMONAVIY BAHOLASH FAOLIYATIDA PYTHON DASTURLASH TILINI QO'LLASHNING USLUBIY ASOSLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	522
Shaminov Abbosjon Faxriddin o'g'li	
MINTAQADA SANOAT TARMOQLARIGA INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB ETISHNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY YO'NALISHLARI.....	527
Maxmudov Jasurbek Ergashevich	
HUDUDIY ASALARICHILIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR VA ULARNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARI	532
Sulaymonov Sherzod Nasivaliyevich	
BARQAROR TURIZM VA UNING IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI	536
Sultonova Abduraimova Kamola Abdumannob qizi	
РАЗВИТИЕ КОРПОРАТИВНЫХ ФИНАНСОВ С УЧЕТОМ ESG-ПРИНЦИПОВ	542
Алиева Сусанна Сейрановна	
ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ РУКОВОДИТЕЛЯ КАК ФАКТОР ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	548
Алибекова Паризода Раджаб кизи, Алимова Машхура Тоирхоновна	
KREDIT RESURSLARINING HUDUDIY IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIKNING INSTITUTIONAL ROLI	554
G'aniyev Sanjar Poziljon o'g'li	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INVESTITSİYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH	561
Qorabayev Shuxratjon Axmadjonovich	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH ORQALI INKLYUZIV INVESTITSION MUHITNI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	568
Irisqulova Munisa Akmal qizi	
AGROKLASTERLARNING TASHKILIY MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	573
Doliyev Samandar Toirovich	
MINTAQADA IQTISODIYOT TARMOQLARINI DIVERSIFIKATSİYALASH USULLARI.....	579
Sapayev Azamat Rustamovich	
MAKROIQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA TASHQI SAVDO SIYOSATINING O'RNI	583
Rustamova Nodira	
GAVKUSHON ANSAMBLI MISOLIDA BUXORO TARIXIY MARKAZIDAGI MEROS OBYEKTLARINING TURISTIK SIG'IM SALOHİYATI.....	587
Xolmurodova Moxichehra Dilmurodovna, Qilichov Muhriddin Husniddin o'g'li	
ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ МНОЖЕСТВЕННОГО КОРРЕЛЯЦИОННО-РЕГРЕССИОННОГО АНАЛИЗА С ПОМОЩЬЮ ПРИКЛАДНЫХ ПРОГРАММ	594
Ганиева Зулфия Самиевна	
XIZMATLAR SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IJTIMOY AHAMIYATI	600
G'aniyev M., Vannobova Gulhayo Tolibjon qizi	
BUXORO TARIXIY MARKAZIDAGI ABDULAZIZXON VA ULUG'BEK MADRASALARINING TURISTIK SIG'IM IMKONIYATLARINI BAHOLASH	604
Ro'ziqulova Feruza Qurbon qizi, Qilichov Muhriddin Husniddin o'g'li	
KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI MOLIVAVIY RAG'BATLANTIRISH HAMDA KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISHNING IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI	612
Iskandarov Saidazamxon Salohiddin o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA NOSTANDART BANDLIK ASOSIDA KICHIK BIZNES RIVOJINI BAHOLASHNING ILMIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI.....	621
Fayzullayev Nurulla Baxromovich	
O'ZBEKISTONNING QAYTA TIKLANADIGAN ENERGIYA MANBALARIGA O'TISHI: MUAMMOLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	627
Ro'ziyeva Dilobar Isomjonovna, Jo'ramurodova Feruza Mardon qizi	

XARAJATLARNI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY YONDASHUVLARI VA USULLARI	633
Toshimov Azizbek Hakimovich	
ГЛОБАЛЬНАЯ КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ МОДЕЛЕЙ РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ ИИ И ЕЁ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ПРОМЫШЛЕННУЮ ПОЛИТИКУ РАЗВИВАЮЩИХСЯ СТРАН	636
Рахматов Феруз Касымович, Садикова Дилафруз Ражабовна, Рахматов Фирдавс Феруз угли	
NODIR DEVONBEGI XONAQOHIDA TURISTIK SIG'IMNI BAHOLASH: FIZIK VA HAQIQIY SIG'IM TAHLILI	647
Odilova Muattar Akram qizi, Qilichov Muhriddin Husniddin o'g'li	
"O'ZBEKISTON – 2030" STRATEGIYASIDA IJTIMOY HIMOYA TIZIMINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	654
Zoya Xalekeyeva, Jamgirbaeva Nilufar Dauilbay qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON SUVEREN XALQARO OBLIGATSIYALARINING NISBATAN PAST FOIZ STAVKADA JOYLASHTIRILISHI: INVESTORLAR ISHONCHI VA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQARORLIK IFODASI	662
Toyirov Yunus Alamovich, Nazarov Qilich Xolmuradovich	
РОЛЬ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО ЧТЕНИЯ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МАРКЕТИНГОВОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ	668
Усманова Зумрад Исламовна	
ДИЛЕММА ПЛАТОНА И ПОППЕРА: ИНТУИЦИЯ КАК АБСОЛЮТНАЯ РАЦИОНАЛЬНОСТЬ	673
Мулладжанова Хосият Яздонова	
IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOTGA ERISHISHDA ERKIN IQTISODIY HUDUDLAR: KECHA, BUGUN VA ISTIQBOL	678
Boboqulov Sanjar Bahromqulovich	
MILLIY VALYUTA KURSI DINAMIKASINING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI	684
Kurbanov Feruz Pirnazarovich, Xudaybergenov Yusufboy Murodovich	
QURILISHDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK	690
B.K.Abdusamatov, F.Ablakulov	
NNTLARNING IJTIMOY AHAMIYATGA MOLIK LOYIHALARINI DAVLAT GRANTI SHAKLIDA MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING RAQAMLI MEKANIZMLARI	695
Xasanov Jahongir Botir o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA BAZEL III STANDARTLARINING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI	701
Absamatov Anvar Ergashevich	
B-READY XALQARO MEZONI: KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	706
Matniyozova Dilrabo Abdug'aprovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA XIZMATLAR SOHASINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISH ISTIQBOLLARI	711
D.A. Togayeva	
ORGANIK QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARINI SERTIFIKATLASH TIZIMI: YEVROPA ITTIFOQI TAJIRIBASI VA O'ZBEKISTON EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	715
Dexkanova Shodiyona Kaxramon qizi, Axmedov Eldor Toyirovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA MAKROIQTISODIY KO'RSATKICHLAR BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH MEZONLARI	720
Kantureeva Asem Jambil qizi, Xudoyqulov Xurshid Xurramovich	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIYOTNING TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARINI INSON KAPITALI ORQALI RAG'BATLANTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI	727
Xudayberganova Nazokat Shonazarovna, Masharipova Xosiyat Matrasulovna	
ЦИФРОВАЯ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ГИДРОЭНЕРГЕТИКИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПЕРЕХОДА К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ	733
Габбарова Ильмира Володиевна	

AUDITORLIK XULOSASI HAMDA AXBOROT TAQDIMOTI SIFATINI INTEGRATSIYALASH AHAMIYATI VA YO'LLARI.....	738
Parpiyev Jaxongir Ilxomjonovich	
INTEGRATION OF TRADE MARKETING AND E-COMMERCE: COMBINING ONLINE AND OFFLINE SALES CHANNELS.....	744
Mamatkulova Shoira Jalolovna	
RAQAMLI TURIZM INFRATUZILMASINI BAHOLASHDA INTEGRATSION INDIKATORLAR TIZIMINI SHAKLLANTIRISH	750
Raximov Abror Zafarovich	
THE ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE OF DEVELOPING PILGRIMAGE TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN	754
Rajapova Gulnoza Maxmudovna	
ЦИФРОВАЯ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ЛЁГКОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ: МИРОВОЙ ОПЫТ И ПРАКТИКА УЗБЕКИСТАНА	759
Ахмедова Газиза Азим кизи	
THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITALIZATION METHODS AND SUSTAINABILITY IN PROVIDING PRODUCTS AND SERVICES TO CUSTOMERS	763
Umarova Nargiza Mirakabarovna	
NOMINAL ALMASHUV KURSI QADRSIZLANISHINING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI: O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA ILMIY-TAHLILII YONDASHUV	768
Toyirov Yunus Alamovich, Nazarov Qilich Xolmuradovich	
СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ КРЕДИТНЫМ ПОРТФЕЛЕМ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	773
Жураева Нодирахон Фузулий кизи	
MILLIY INNOVATSION TIZIMDA FAN TA'LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH O'ZARO UYG'UNLIGI	779
Uzaydullayev Sherzod Shukurullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM SOHASIDA INNOVATSIYALARNING AHAMIYATI VA ULARNING TURIZM RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI	782
To'raboyeva Kimiyoxon O'rozbekovna, Asadov Baxshullo Xasanboy o'g'li	
DAVLAT QARZI VA UNING RIVOJLANAYOTGAN MAMLAKATLARDI IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI.....	786
Alimov Muhammad Yunus Muhammad ali o'g'li	
RAQAMLI BOSHQARUV VA TASHKILII-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLAR ORQALI MINTAQAVII OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	791
Dilmurodov Zuhridin Do'stmurod o'g'li	
MAHALLA INSTITUTIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA OILAVII TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISHNING TASHKILII-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARI	795
Dawletmuratov Adilbay Mirzabaevich	
MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TASHQI SAVDO OPERATSIYALARINI RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA QILISH ASOSLARI	801
Masharipova Manzura Alimbayevna	
ME'ROS OBYEKTLARIDA TURISTIK SIG'IMNI MIQDORII BAHOLASH: NODIR DEVONBEGI MADRASASI MISOLIDA	806
Ikromova Shaxinabonu Ilg'or qizi, Qilichov Muhriddin Husniddin o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH: MUAMMOLAR VA YECHIMLAR.....	813
Hujamuradov Abrorbek Ro'zimurat o'g'li	

THE ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE OF DEVELOPING PILGRIMAGE TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article scientifically analyzes the economic significance of developing pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan. Pilgrimage tourism, as one of the strategic directions based on the country's cultural and religious heritage, plays an important role in regional economic growth, increasing employment, and diversifying the services sector. The study examines the current situation, identifies key issues, and develops scientifically grounded proposals for further development.

Key words: pilgrimage tourism, economic diversification, tourism policy, regional development, services sector.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda ziyorat turizmini rivojlantirishning iqtisodiy ahamiyati ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilingan. Ziyorat turizmi mamlakatning boy madaniy va diniy merosiga asoslangan strategik yo'nalishlardan biri sifatida hududiy iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlash, bandlik darajasini oshirish hamda xizmatlar sohasini diversifikatsiya qilishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Tadqiqotda sohaning bugungi holati tahlil qilinib, mavjud muammolar aniqlangan hamda uni rivojlantirish bo'yicha ilmiy asoslangan takliflar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ziyorat turizmi, iqtisodiy diversifikatsiya, turizm siyosati, hududiy rivojlanish, xizmatlar sohasi.

Аннотация. В данной статье научно анализируется экономическое значение развития паломнического туризма в Узбекистане. Паломнический туризм, являясь одним из стратегических направлений, основанных на богатом культурном и религиозном наследии страны, играет важную роль в обеспечении регионального экономического роста, повышении уровня занятости и диверсификации сферы услуг. В исследовании анализируется текущее состояние отрасли, выявляются существующие проблемы и разрабатываются научно обоснованные предложения по её дальнейшему развитию.

Ключевые слова: паломнический туризм, экономическая диверсификация, туристическая политика, региональное развитие, сфера услуг.

INTRODUCTION

The tourism sector in the global economic system is recognized as one of the strategic industries that stimulates economic growth, generates significant income, and ensures employment. Over the past decades, the growth of tourism service exports, the increase in international tourist flows, and the expansion of the services sector have further strengthened the role of this industry in the global economy. Especially in developing countries, tourism is regarded as an important factor of economic diversification, serving as an alternative source of income alongside traditional industries.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, tourism development has also been identified as one of the priority directions of state economic policy. In recent years, systematic reforms have been implemented in the country to modernize tourism infrastructure, liberalize the visa regime, expand international transport connections, and develop a national tourism brand. As a result of these measures, Uzbekistan's competitiveness in the international tourism market has increased, and steady growth in tourist flows has been observed.

Among the structural directions of tourism, pilgrimage tourism occupies a special place. Pilgrimage tourism, based on religious and spiritual values, is important not only for preserving cultural heritage but also for stimulating economic development. The numerous sacred sites located in Uzbekistan, including pilgrimage destinations associated with great scholars such as Imam al-Bukhari, Bahauddin Naqshband, and Abu Mansur al-Maturidi, create significant opportunities for transforming the country into one of the international centers of pilgrimage tourism.

In March 2026, the Islamic Civilization Center was opened in Tashkent. This large scientific and educational complex, dedicated to the history of Islam in Central Asia, has already become an attractive destination for tourists.

The complex, built over nearly eight years, includes a museum, a library, and scientific and educational spaces. Its main exhibitions include the Quran Hall, which houses the Uthman Mushaf, as well as sections devoted to pre-Islamic culture, the scientific flourishing of the 9th–13th centuries, the Timurid era, and the modern development of Uzbekistan.

The center also serves as a scientific hub: international forums are held there, and an expert council operates with the participation of organizations such as IRCICA, ICESCO, and the Oxford Centre for Islamic Studies [1].

Pilgrimage tourism is an important factor in ensuring the diversification of the national economy. This sector creates new jobs, develops the services sector, modernizes regional infrastructure, and increases local budget revenues [2].

From this perspective, a comprehensive study of the economic significance of developing pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan, an analysis of its impact on regional development, the identification of existing issues, and the development of scientifically grounded proposals to address them are relevant scientific and practical tasks. This research is devoted precisely to these issues.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Scientific research on the impact of tourism on economic development has been conducted extensively. According to reports by the World Tourism Organization, the tourism sector represents an important part of global services exports and is considered one of the key factors contributing to economic growth and employment in many countries [3].

The multiplier effect of tourism has been widely studied by C. Michael Hall, who emphasizes that tourism infrastructure has a significant impact on regional development and investment activity [4]. In addition, the works of Melanie Smith highlight the role of cultural and pilgrimage tourism in economic and social integration [5].

In the scientific literature on pilgrimage tourism, the distinctive features of this field have been studied separately. Researchers assess pilgrimage tourism as an important component of sustainable tourism, emphasizing its role in preserving cultural heritage, developing the local economy, and strengthening social stability. In particular, it has been scientifically substantiated that the development of religious tourism contributes to the expansion of the services sector in regions, the activation of small business entities, and the improvement of infrastructure.

Issues related to tourism development in Uzbekistan have also been widely covered in studies conducted by local scholars. In particular, these studies highlight the need to modernize tourism infrastructure, improve service quality, and strengthen competitiveness in the international tourism market. At the same time, some studies emphasize that the economic potential of pilgrimage tourism has not yet been sufficiently explored, particularly due to the limited number of analyses conducted at the regional level.

The analysis shows that although the general economic impact of pilgrimage tourism has been addressed in existing scientific works, a comprehensive assessment of its impact on regional economic diversification, especially at the level of individual regions, remains insufficiently developed. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the economic significance of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan at the regional level and to develop scientifically grounded conclusions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed methods of statistical data analysis, comparative analysis, and systematic analysis. The research findings were generalized on the basis of official statistical sources, national reports, and international analytical materials.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Despite the decline caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the rapid recovery of the tourism sector confirms that it is a stable and promising industry in the economy.

In recent years, tourist flows to the Republic of Uzbekistan and the volume of tourism services exports from foreign tourists have increased significantly (Table 1).

Table 1. Number of Foreign Tourists Visiting the Republic of Uzbekistan (thousands)

№	Year	Total number of tourists
1.	2012	1895
2.	2013	1968.6
3.	2014	1862
4.	2015	1917.7
5.	2016	2027
6.	2017	2690
7.	2018	5346.3
8.	2019	6748.5
9.	2020	1504.1
10.	2021	1881.3
11.	2022	5232.8
12.	2023	6626.3
13.	2024	7957.2
14.	2025	11679.6

Source: Compiled by the author based on data from the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan [6]

As can be seen from this table, in 2025 a total of 11,679.6 thousand tourists visited the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is an almost 1.5-fold increase compared to the same period of the previous year, i.e., in 2024 a total of 7,957.2 thousand tourists visited.

This growth indicates the development of tourism infrastructure in the region and the effectiveness of state policy (Figure 1).

International tourists flow (Thousand people)

Figure 1. Growth Dynamics of Tourist Flows in the Republic of Uzbekistan (2012-2025)¹

Analysis of the chart data shows that during the observed period the tourism sector developed consistently, while in certain years a significant growth trend was recorded.

During 2012–2016, the flow of foreign tourists remained relatively stable, with indicators ranging from approximately 1.8 to 2 million visitors. During this period, the gradual development of tourism infrastructure and the existing visa procedures limited the rapid expansion of tourist flows.

¹ Source: Compiled by the author based on data from the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan [6]

Beginning in 2017, substantial growth was observed as a result of comprehensive reforms implemented in the tourism sector. In particular, while the number of tourists reached 2.69 million in 2017, this figure increased sharply in 2018, exceeding 5.3 million visitors. In 2019, the flow of foreign tourists reached 6.7 million, representing one of the highest growth indicators during the analyzed period. This positive trend can be explained by the simplification of visa procedures, the expansion of international air connections, and the active promotion of Uzbekistan in the international tourism market.

In 2020, the tourism sector experienced a temporary decline due to the global COVID-19 pandemic, and tourist flows decreased to 1.5 million. Restrictions introduced during the pandemic significantly affected international tourism activity worldwide.

From 2021 onward, the tourism sector gradually entered a recovery phase. The number of tourists exceeded 5.2 million in 2022, reached 6.6 million in 2023, and approached 8 million in 2024. According to available data, by 2025 the flow of foreign tourists exceeded 11.6 million visitors. These indicators demonstrate the steadily increasing potential of tourism in Uzbekistan, particularly in the fields of pilgrimage and cultural tourism (Figure 2).

Tourism services export volume (USD million)

Figure 2. Volume of Tourism Services Exports in the Republic of Uzbekistan (2010-2024)²

According to the results for 2025, the export of services provided to tourists in Uzbekistan reached 4.8 billion US dollars, and this indicator grew by 142.2 percent.

In general, the chart analysis confirms that the tourism sector in Uzbekistan has a steady growth trend and that this direction is becoming one of the important drivers of economic development.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conducted analyses show that there are several systemic issues in the process of developing pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan, which limit the full realization of this sector's economic potential.

First, the uneven development of tourism infrastructure across regions remains one of the key issues. In particular, in some regions with significant pilgrimage tourism potential, transport systems, accommodation facilities, and service industries require further modernization and expansion. This situation affects the sustainable growth of tourist flows.

Second, certain challenges related to service quality and standardization are still observed. The adaptation of tourism services to international standards, the training of qualified personnel, and the further development of service culture are important factors for strengthening the competitiveness of pilgrimage tourism.

Third, the marketing and branding system also requires further improvement. Uzbekistan's pilgrimage tourism potential has substantial opportunities for broader promotion in the international tourism market, which would contribute to more effective utilization of the country's rich cultural and spiritual heritage.

² Source: Compiled by the author based on data from the National Statistics Committee and Tourism Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan [6,7]

Fourth, there is a need to diversify tourism products more extensively. In many cases, pilgrimage tourism is mainly associated with religious visits, while integrating it with cultural, gastronomic, and ecotourism directions could increase tourists' length of stay and improve economic efficiency.

To address the identified issues and increase the economic effectiveness of pilgrimage tourism, the following scientifically grounded proposals are recommended.

First, comprehensive modernization of tourism infrastructure should be continued. In particular, improving the transport and logistics system, increasing the number of modern hotels and family guesthouses, and upgrading roads leading to pilgrimage destinations should remain priority tasks.

Second, improving the system of personnel training is essential for enhancing service quality. Introducing educational programs that meet international standards for tourism specialists, along with organizing practical training courses, would contribute significantly to sector development.

Third, it is important to develop effective marketing strategies for promoting pilgrimage tourism internationally. In this regard, broader use of digital marketing tools and active promotion of the national tourism brand through social media and international platforms are highly important.

Fourth, diversification of tourism products should be regarded as a strategic direction. Developing integrated tourism packages that combine pilgrimage tourism with cultural, gastronomic, and ecotourism routes would increase overall economic efficiency.

Fifth, expanding public-private partnership mechanisms to attract investment into the tourism sector is advisable. This approach would contribute to accelerating infrastructure development and improving service quality.

The results of the conducted research show that pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan is not only a sphere of cultural and spiritual significance, but also an important strategic sector contributing to the sustainable development of the national economy. The development of this direction directly influences the expansion of the services sector, the growth of regional economic activity, and the creation of new jobs.

The analyses indicate that pilgrimage tourism serves as an important driver of economic diversification, enabling the effective involvement of regional resources in economic circulation. Particularly in regions rich in historical and religious heritage, tourism development contributes to the activation of small business and private entrepreneurship.

At the same time, existing sectoral challenges — including infrastructure limitations, service quality issues, marketing system development, and the need for broader diversification of tourism products — continue to influence the full realization of pilgrimage tourism's economic potential.

By systematically addressing these issues, Uzbekistan's pilgrimage tourism can become a competitive segment in the global tourism market. In this regard, a comprehensive approach involving infrastructure modernization, digital marketing development, enhancement of personnel capacity, and expansion of public-private partnership mechanisms is of great importance.

In general, pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan's economy should be regarded not only as an additional source of income, but also as a strategic direction for regional economic development and diversification. The scientific and systematic development of this sector will contribute to the country's long-term economic stability and sustainable growth.

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